

Factors Affecting Project Scheduling Of Non-Governmental Organizations' Projects in Mogadishu, Somalia. (A Case Study of International Rescue Committee)

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Maina Tabitha Wanja, MSC Project Management Student, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology ⁽²⁾Dr. Mike A. Iravo (PhD), Lecturer, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to assess factors affecting project scheduling of non-governmental organizations' projects in Mogadishu, Somalia. (A Case Study Of International Rescue Committee).The study was informed by the theory of performance and agency theory. The research design that the study adopted is the descriptive survey design. The target population for the study consists of 52 Humanitarian officers operating in Mogadishu working for the International Rescue Committee (IRC). The study adopted census and include every member in the sample from in the study. The main data collection tool for the study was the questionnaire. The collected data was analysed through descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistical tools that the study used included frequencies, percentages and mean while inferential statistical tools included regression analysis. Results obtained from monitoring and evaluation process provided a crucial link between project implementers and decision-makers. Good stakeholder participation program enabled those who are interested in, or affected by a decision, have an opportunity to influence the outcome and that management' commitment ensured timely completion of NGO initiated projects. The study concludes that monitoring and evaluation and stakeholders' commitment influenced scheduling of NGO Projects in Mogadishu. Monitoring and evaluation of NGO Projects in Mogadishu should be performed in every phase of implementation. Project implementation team should fully engage all the stakeholders in projects implementation process.

Keywords: Monitoring and evaluation, Project implementation, NGO, project scheduling and stakeholders' commitment

Introduction

The project schedule is a tool that communicates what work needs to be performed, which resources of the organization will perform the work and the timeframes in which that work needs to be performed. The project schedule reflects all of the work associated with delivering the project on time. Without a full and complete schedule, the project manager will be unable to communicate the complete effort, in terms of cost and resources, necessary to deliver the project. The project schedule provides a roadmap for tasks and milestones that are tracked and controlled as the project proceeds and it is based on the information provided by the people completing the tasks. Project schedule prevents against delays in implementation of the projects caused by unrealistic deadline established by outsiders, changing customer requirements that are not reflected in the schedule and sometimes an honest underestimate of effort and/or resources required. In addition, delays could be caused by risks that were not considered when the project, technical difficulties that could not have been foreseen and any other human difficulties that could not have been foreseen (Bhatti, 2013).

Projects schedules are influenced by a multiple of factors, which can be external or internal to the organization responsible for its management and execution. These include poor project management, inadequate opportunities for potential beneficiaries to participate in project identification and design, poor linkages between project activities and project purpose, insufficient attention to external environment during project design, among others (Buckhout, 2009).

Projects remain the instruments of choice for policymakers in national and international development. In Africa and other third world countries, development projects play a great role in providing basic social services such as infrastructure building, provision of basic education, agricultural extension, raising public awareness on different development issues such as gender equity, environmental protection. In particular, development projects aims at filling development gap where governments fall short. However, the poor performance of projects and the disappointment of project stakeholders and beneficiaries are always apparent and common in numerous projects (Kwak, 2002).

According to the World Bank, the project failure rate in African countries was over 50% by the year 2000 this was according to Meltzer Commission Report, 2000. Kwak (2002), points out that in most cases World Bank projects fail to achieve their goals due to problems that could be termed as managerial and organizational issues. Specifically, managerial and organizational issues can further be broken down into imperfect project design, poor stakeholder management, delays between project identification and start-up, delays during project implementation, cost overruns, coordination failure, and so forth (Youker, 1999; Fortune & White, 2006, 2000; Gunawan & Ahsan, 2010).

The strength and opportunities are positive forces that should be exploited to efficiently implement a project. The weaknesses and threats are hindrances that can hamper project implementation. The implementers should ensure that they devise means of overcoming them. Monitoring is important at this implementation phase to ensure that the project is implemented as per the schedule. This is a continuous process that should be put in place before project implementation starts. As such, the monitoring activities should appear on the work plan and should involve all stake holders. If activities are not going on well, arrangements should be made to identify the problem so that they can be corrected. Monitoring is also important to ensure that activities are implemented as planned. This helps the implementers to measure how well they are achieving their targets. This is based on the understanding that the process through which a project is implemented has a lot of effect on its use, operation and maintenance (Graham and Englund, 1997). Project implementation therefore requires genuine commitment to both the donor and the recipient country. This is often lacking, ultimately leaving most of the already started project to tarry from implementation.

Globally, a number of projects continue to fall below their targets. A lot of invested funds in these projects have gone down the drain with no tangible outcomes or results. In Somalia, a number of projects that have been futile ventures in relation to their objectives. The underperformance of these projects terribly affects both NGO program operations. UN habitat project evaluation teams have found lack of quality documentary evidence across various projects and activities evaluated. For instance, many projects in Somali have no monitoring or progress midterm or terminal evaluation reports to ascertain success of the projects. The overall performance of a project is a key factor to ascertain the implementation of a project. This is usually determined by the attainment of the project objectives and the sustainability of the project thereafter.

There is a very great need for these projects to have an impact in the local community in Somali. A country where women's social indicators consistently lag behind those of men. For instance, the adult literacy rate is estimated to be 27 percent for females compared with 50 percent for males. The gross enrolment rate for girls is 15 percent compared with 27 percent for boys. It is estimated that 98 percent of Somali women and girls have undergone some form of genital mutilation. Moreover, a household survey in Hargeisa, Somali found that up to 25 percent of households claim remittances as their sole source of income. Another study in by Burco and Bossaso (2014), found that 40 percent of Somali households benefited from the money sent by the diaspora and 80 percent of the start-up capital for small and medium-sized businesses in Somalia came from remittances. These statistics indicate that there is need for the projects initiated by NGOs in Somali to have an impact in their social and economic systems.

The number of projects initiated by various NGOs in various parts of Somalia forms a worthy spectrum for analysis. The Somalia NGO Consortium reported that there have been 158 NGOs registered in Somali, but shockingly almost 85% of these NGOs wrapped up their operations long time ago without making any impact in relation to the objectives they were pursuing. The resources committed by the UN habitat to the various projects were enormous but their impact was negligible while active ones have produced wonderful results, proving a great success. A number of implementation or execution drawbacks have hindered the success of these programs. Challenges of insecurity, fraud, inadequate planning, poor identification of target beneficiaries and poor infrastructure as well as logistical challenges delay effective implementation leading delays, increased costs and variation of the scope of these programs.

Chen (2014) studied project selection, scheduling and resource allocation for engineering design groups. Also, Hietala (2013) did a study to establish quality of project schedules in industrial projects. Locally, Owour (2016) did a study to establish factors influencing completion of construction projects in Nairobi

County, Kenya. Further, Nthiga (2013) did a study to establish the Determinants of project schedule control during project implementation in Mbeere North district, Embu County.. These studies have identified and documented various factors that have influenced project scheduling and its implementation however; none has carried out a specific study focusing on the influence funding, monitoring and evaluation, stakeholders and management commitment that are key in project scheduling. This study therefore intends to investigate how these factors affect project schedule of Non-Governmental Organizations' Projects in Mogadishu Somalia. Thus, this study objectives are:

1. *To determine the effect of monitoring and evaluation on project scheduling of NGO Projects in Mogadishu.*
2. *To establish the effect of stakeholders commitment on project scheduling of NGO Projects in Mogadishu.*

Theoretical review

This paper was anchored on Resource dependency theory. This theory was proposed by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978). The theory is the study of how the external resources of organizations affect the behavior of the organization. Resource dependence generally attributes motives of power and control to the formation of inter-organizational arrangements. The idea of interdependence lies at the heart of resource dependence that is a consequence of the open-systems nature of organizations' (Seo, 2011). It focuses on resources that an organization must acquire from external sources for its survival or success (Irfan, 2015). The need to acquire resources creates interdependencies between organizations. Although such interdependencies could be symmetric in nature as in the case of reciprocal exchange of resources, a resource dependence perspective argues that organizations must strive to decrease dependence on other organizations by securing control over critical resources (Seo, 2011). Moreover, an organization should also acquire control over resources required by other organizations in order to increase their dependence. The formation of partnership is generally seen as a mechanism to gain access to important resources held by others.

NGO in nature have high dependability on donor funding (Lekorwe & Mpabanga, 2007). Like other NGOs, International Rescue Committee depend on resources that ultimately originate from an organization's environment which to a considerable extent, contains other organizations. Such funding organisations make part of stakeholders in the NGO operating environment. Further, these resources are basis of power for the NGOs and helps them to meet their objectives. As such, this theory helps to explain the role of funding and stakeholder involvement play in an effective project scheduling of NGO Projects in Mogadishu.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework diagram

Literature review**Monitoring and Control Process**

According to Tetteh(2014), good planning, monitoring and evaluation enhance the contribution of NGOs by establishing clear links between past, present and future initiatives and development results. Monitoring and evaluation can help an organization extract relevant information from past and ongoing activities that may be the as the basis for programmatic fine-tuning, reorientation and future planning. Without effective planning, monitoring and evaluation, it would be impossible to judge if work is going in the right direction, whether progress and success can be claimed, and how future efforts might be improved. While monitoring provides real-time information required by management, evaluation provides more in-depth assessment. The monitoring process can generate questions to be answered by evaluation. In addition, evaluation draws heavily on data generated through monitoring during the programme and project cycle, including, for example, baseline data, information on the programme or project implementation process and measurements of results (Don, 2011).

Crawford et al., (2005), supposed that the monitoring and controlling process consists of those processes required to track, review, and regulate the progress and performance of the project; identify any areas in which changes to the plan are required; and initiate the corresponding changes. The key benefit of this process is that project performance is observed and measured regularly and consistently to identify variances from the project schedule. The monitoring and controlling process also includes: controlling changes and recommending preventive action in anticipation of possible problems, monitoring the ongoing project activities against the project management plan and the project performance baseline, and influencing the factors that could circumvent integrated change control so only approved changes are implemented.

This continuous monitoring provides the project team insight into the health of the project and identifies any areas requiring additional attention. The Monitoring and Controlling process not only monitors and controls the work done at a point in time, but also monitors and controls the entire project effort (Meyer, 2007). In multi-phase projects, the Monitoring and Controlling process coordinates project phases in order to implement corrective or preventive actions to bring the project into compliance with the project management plan. This review can result in recommended and approved updates to the project management plan. For example, a missed activity finish date may require adjustments to the current staffing plan, reliance on overtime, or tradeoffs between budget and schedule objectives.

Project monitoring and control ensures effectiveness and efficiency of operations, reliability of project outcomes, promoting compliance with regulations, protecting resources and reducing risk of fraud and corruption (Gregory, 2005). Internal control systems should be put in place to provide reasonable assurance regarding the responsible use of project assets .Furthermore, poor or excessive internal controls reduce productivity, increase the complexity of systems, increase the time required to complete processes and add no value to the activities.

A monitoring and evaluation entity that functions at different levels, for example at the project, programme or outcome level, should have a clear guideline outlining its role and responsibilities. State how it will set up systematic monitoring frameworks and develop an evaluation plan. The entities ought to meet regularly with key partners and stakeholders to assess progress towards achieving the results and conducting joint field monitoring and evaluation missions to assess achievements and constraints (Payne & Turner, 2009). In addition, identify any lessons or good practices and reflect on how well the results achieved are addressing gender, and the interests and rights of marginalized and vulnerable groups in the society. Moreover, they should be in the forefront of identifying additional capacity development needs among stakeholders and partners and reporting regularly to the lead individuals or agencies for the particular result areas and seeking opportunities to influence policy and decision-making processes (Golini & Landoni, 2014).Phiri (2005) conducted a research to investigate the influence of monitoring and evaluation on project performance. Statistically, the study showed that there was a positive correlation between M&E and project performance. Among monitoring and evaluation activities, monitoring and evaluation planning and training have a significant correlation with project performance. However, the study only focused more on determining

what influence monitoring and evaluation has on project performance. No consideration was made on other factors that are key in determining the performance of projects.

Stakeholder Participation

Throughout all stages of planning, monitoring, evaluating, learning and improving a project schedule, it is vital to engage stakeholders, promote buy-in and commitment, and motivate action. A strong results-management process aims to engage stakeholders in thinking as openly and creatively as possible about what they want to achieve and encourage them to organize themselves to achieve what they have agreed on, including putting in place a process to monitor and evaluate progress and use the information to improve performance (Beck, 2006).

Meyer (2007), has argued that inadequate stakeholder involvement is one of the most common reasons programmes and projects fail. Therefore, every effort should be made to encourage broad and active stakeholder engagement in the planning, monitoring and evaluation processes. This is particularly relevant to crisis situations where people's sense of security and vulnerability may be heightened and where tensions and factions may exist. In these situations, the planning process should aim to ensure that as many stakeholders as possible are involved (especially those who may be least able to promote their own interests), and that opportunities are created for the various parties to hear each other's perspectives in an open and balanced manner. In crisis situations this is not just good practice but is fundamental to ensuring that programming 'does no harm' at the least and, hopefully, reduces inherent or active tensions (Slevin, 2009).

According to Wang and Huang (2006), perceptions of NGOs neutrality, and at times the success of the programme or project, depend on representatives of the different main stakeholder groups (including those relating to different parties of the tension) being equally consulted. In some situations, planning brings stakeholders together so that they can hear each other's views may itself be a mechanism for reducing tensions. Project stakeholder is any party with an interest in the project process or outcome (Maylor, 2010). Thus, those individuals, groups, or organizations, which are actively involved or are interested in the result of the project. Stakeholder management is crucial to the success of every project in every organization, and engaging the right people at the right time is very important to a project's success.

Jiang, Klein, Wu, and Liang (2009) on the other hand carried out a study on how environmental factors affect the performance of the project manager. They identified thirteen factors that affect performance: job related factors were salary, job satisfaction, job security, availability of information; project related factors were, project environment, project size, time availability, complexity of project, team relationship, materials and supplies and duration of project, while organization-related factors were, level of authority and type of client.

Materials and methods

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population of this study are 52 International Rescue Committee (IRC) employees working in Mogadishu Somalia on the 5 projects it has on health, power, education, economic well-being and safety. All the 52 subjects were taken from the population. This was considered adequate for generalization. The main data collection tool for the study was the questionnaire. The research instruments were pretested on 10 respondents from Red Cross, Kenya. This was to ascertain the thinking behind the answers so that the researcher can accurately assess whether the questionnaires were filled out properly, whether the questions were actually understood by respondents, and whether the questions are what the researcher intends. To establish the validity of the research instrument the researcher sought the opinions of experts in the field of study especially the researcher's supervisor and lecturers. This facilitated the necessary revision and modification of the research instruments thereby enhancing validity. The reliability and Internal consistency is calculated by measuring a statistic known as the Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951; Nunally, 1978), which reflects the homogeneity of a scale. According to Nunally (1978), Cronbach's alpha is considered a good measure of reliability in social science research when it is found to be .70 or above. The higher the Cronbach's alpha (close to 1) in relation to an

instrument is found to be, the more reliable the instrument. Data was coded and entered into Statistical Packages for Social Scientists (SPSS Version 21.0) and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The researcher further employed regression model to study the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables.

Findings and Discussion

Sample Characteristics

Results obtained show that (77.8%) of the respondents were males whereas 22.2% were females. most of the (28.9%) respondents were aged between 45 to 55 years, 26.7% of the respondents were aged over 55 years, 24.4% of the respondents were aged between 35 to 45 years while 20.0 % of the respondents were aged between 25 to 35 years, Results obtained show that most of the respondents (33.3%) held college diploma certificates, 31.1% of the respondents held bachelors degree, 22.2% of the respondents held high school certificate, while 13.3% of the respondents held post graduate. Results obtained from the analysis show that 33.3% of the respondents had served in the current position for a period of 48.9% of the respondents had served for a period of 17.8% indicated 1 year to 5years, while 17.8% indicated 1 year to 5years. Results obtained from the analysis show that 44.4% of the respondents indicate More than 10 years, 40.0% of the respondents indicated 5 years to 10 years while 15.6% 1 year to 5years. This implies that majority of the respondents had considerable work which implies that information they gave could be reliable depending on their vast knowledge with running on organisational affairs,

Descriptive statistics

Monitoring and evaluation

The study sought to determine the extent to which respondents agreed with the following statements assessing the relationship between monitoring and evaluation and project scheduling. Result are analysed in Table 1 Results obtained show that, majority of the respondents agreed that; timely corrective actions to improve project performance avoids project completion delays at later stages (mean = 4.23, std deviation = 0.32), monitoring and evaluation provide relevant information from past and ongoing project that may be the as the basis for programmatic fine-tuning, reorientation and future planning to ensure timely completion (mean = 4.15, std deviation = 0.12) and that performance evaluation feedback improves project schedule performance (mean = 3.96 , std deviation =0.93). The findings are in line with the study findings by Channah Sorah, (2013), that timely evaluation of information throughout the life cycle is critical in measuring project performance

The study also revealed that timely completion of NGO projects depends on effective monitoring and evaluation, without monitoring and evaluation, it would be impossible to judge if work is completed within timelines (mean = 3.87, std deviation = 0.92) monitoring and evaluation process coordinates project phases in order to ensure timely completion (mean = 3.83, std deviation = 0.89) and that project monitoring and evaluation ensures effectiveness and efficiency of operations relevant to timely project completion (mean = 3.76, std deviation = 0.71). The findings are in line with the research Tetteh (2014), timely monitoring and evaluation was essential in stimulating positive change in project implementation

Table 1: Monitoring and evaluation and project scheduling

	Mean	SD
Timely completion of our NGO projects depends on effective monitoring and evaluation	3.87	0.92
Performance evaluation feedback improves project schedule performance	3.96	0.93
Timely corrective actions to improve project performance avoids project completion delays at later stages	4.23	0.32
Monitoring and evaluation provide relevant information from past and ongoing project that may be the as the basis for programmatic fine-tuning, reorientation and future planning to ensure timely completion	4.15	0.12
Without monitoring and evaluation, it would be impossible to judge if work is completed within timelines	3.87	0.92
Monitoring and evaluation process coordinates project phases in order to ensure timely completion	3.83	0.89
Project monitoring and evaluation ensures effectiveness and efficiency of operations relevant to timely project completion	3.76	0.71

Stakeholder Involvement

The study sought to determine the extent to which respondents agreed with the following statements assessing the relationship between stakeholder involvement and project scheduling. Result are analysed in Table 1 From the study results, majority of the respondents agreed that; engaging stakeholders, promote buy-in and commitment, and motivate action for timely completion of projects (mean = 4.42, std deviation = 0.51) and that effective communication updated to all the stakeholders play a big role in determining the projects quality delivery performance (mean = 4.39, std deviation = 0.50) these findings on stakeholder involvement concurs Kobia and Mohammed (2006) who asserts that Stakeholder's participation in the overall design of the strategies to be employed in strategic plans offers invaluable support throughout the execution of the activities

The research also revealed that involving local stakeholders in decision making empowers them and guarantees project objectives (mean = 3.65, std deviation = 0.49) and that Stakeholders involvement especially in crisis situations is important to ensure smooth sailing of the projects for timely delivery. The findings are in line with the study findings by Kimani, (2009) who stated that satisfying key stakeholder requirement is central to achieving a successful project outcome

Table 2: Stakeholder Involvement and project scheduling

	Mean	SD
Engaging stakeholders, promote buy-in and commitment, and motivate action for timely completion of projects	4.42	0.51
Stakeholders involvement especially in crisis situations is important to ensure smooth sailing of the projects for timely delivery	3.52	0.51
Communication updates to all our stakeholders play a big role in determining our projects quality delivery performance	4.39	0.50
Involving local stakeholders in decision making empowers them and guarantees project objectives	3.65	0.49

Schedule Performance of Ngo Projects

This section sought to assess the performance of NGO projects. Result are analysed in Table 3 From the study results, majority of the respondents agreed that; at times NGO initiated projects in Somali experienced cost over runs that affect project schedule performance (mean = 4.43, std deviation = 0.49) and that performance of our projects is normally defined as successful if the intended outcomes are sustainable

(mean = 3.70, std deviation = 0.47) the findings concurs with the study findings by the findings concurs with the study findings by March (2011), that for community based project to be sustainable the stake holders especially the community must be satisfied with the overall management of the project

However respondents disagreed that most of the NGO initiated projects in Somali started and ended at the scheduled time (mean = 1.19, std deviation = 0.20), project meets all the milestones as planned (mean = 1.63, std deviation =0.81). The findings are in line with the research by Dhakal (2007) limited funding is a major factor that negatively influences the scheduling and implementation on NGO process.

Table 3: Statements assessing the performance of NGO projects in Somalia

	Mean	SD
At times projects experience cost over runs that affect project schedule performance	4.43	0.49
Most of our projects start and ends at the scheduled time	1.19	0.20
Our project meets all the milestones as planned	1.63	0.81
Performance of our projects is normally defined as successful if the intended outcomes are sustainable	3.70	0.47

Regression Analysis

In this study, a multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the influence among predictor variables. The research used statistical package for social sciences (SPSS V 22.0) to code, enter and compute the measurements of the multiple regressions. The model summary are presented in the table 4 Adjusted R squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. From the findings in the above table the value of adjusted R squared was 0.772 an indication that there was variation of 77.2 percent on scheduling of NGO projects in Mogadishu due to changes in project funding, monitoring and evaluation, stakeholders commitment and management commitment at 95 percent confidence interval. this shows that 77.2 percent changes in scheduling of NGO projects in Mogadishu could be accounted to project funding, monitoring and evaluation, stakeholders' commitment and management commitment. R is the correlation coefficient which shows the relationship between the study variables, from the findings shown in the table above is notable that there exists strong positive relationship between the study variables as shown by 0.919.

From the ANOVA statics, the study established the regression model had a significance level of 0.1% which is an indication that the data was ideal for making a conclusion on the population parameters as the value of significance (p-value) was less than 5%. The calculated value was greater than the critical value (3.071>1.997) an indication that project funding, monitoring and evaluation, stakeholders commitment and management commitment all influenced scheduling of NGO Projects in Mogadishu. The significance value was less than 0.05 indicating that the model was significant.

Table 4: Regression Results

	Unstandardized		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.431	0.628		2.279	0.001
Monitoring and evaluation	0.657	0.101	0.627	6.505	0.000
Stakeholders commitment	0.586	0.114	0.546	5.14	0.001
R Square	0.844				
Adjusted R Square	0.772				
F	3.071				
Sig.	.001				

From the data in the above table the established regression equation was

$$Y = 1.431 + 0.731X_1 + 0.657 X_2 + 0.586 X_3 + 0.546 X_4$$

From the above regression equation it was revealed that holding project funding, monitoring and evaluation, stakeholders commitment and management commitment, to a constant zero, a unit increase in monitoring and evaluation process would promote scheduling of NGO projects in Mogadishu by a factor of 0.657, a unit increase in stakeholders commitment would promote scheduling of NGO projects in Mogadishu by a factor of 0.586. All the variables were significant as their significant value was less than ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions and Recommendations

The research concludes that monitoring and evaluation is key to successful project scheduling of NGO Projects in Mogadishu. However it's notable that most of the NGO Projects in Mogadishu lacked strong monitoring teams, majority of the monitoring teams lacked adequate M&E skills that matched with the current evaluation dynamics and that very few NGO which had initiated staff capacity building initiatives that would promote project scheduling process. In line with the third objective the study concluded that stakeholders involvement is essential in promoting project scheduling of NGO initiated projects, however the study noted that stakeholders involvement in scheduling of NGO Projects in Mogadishu is below the satisfactory levels.

Monitoring and evaluation of NGO Projects in Mogadishu must be carried out after every phase of implementation. This will be essential in providing information that showcases project scheduling and implementation progress. The monitoring and evaluation team should present the M&E information periodically as this was found to positively influence decision making.

Project implementation team should fully engage all the stakeholders in projects implementation process. The project implementation committee should also encourage stakeholder participation and cooperation through incentives and that Stakeholder role should also be well outlined and communicated in advance to avoid conflicts of interest during implementation phase.

It would also be important to conduct a research on NGO projects that despite receiving enough support and capacity building during implementation still don't sustain itself for long soon after the donors withdraws. Research should be carried to establish how bidding of tenders affects project implementation of NGO Projects in Mogadishu Somalia.

References

- Crawford, P., & Bryce, P. (2005). Project monitoring and evaluation: a method for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of aid project implementation. *International journal of project management*, 21(5), 363-373.
- Jiang, J. J., Klein, G., Wu, S. P., & Liang, T. P. (2009). The relation of requirements uncertainty and stakeholder perception gaps to project management performance. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 82(5), 801-808.
- Maylor, Harvey (2010). *Project Management*. 4th edition. Prentice Hall.
- Meyer, J. (2007) The Use of Cash/Vouchers in Response to Vulnerability and Food Insecurity Case Study Review and Analysis Commissioned by: United Nations World Food Programme
- OCHA (2011b) 'Somalia: Famine and Drought Situation Report No. 17', <http://reliefweb.int/node/452217>, 11 October.
- OCHA (2011c) 'Somalia: Humanitarian Overview', vol. 4, issue 5, <http://reliefweb.int/node/405690>.
- Tetteh, I. (2014). *Use of Project Management Methods*. Master Thesis Faculty of Economics, Masaryk University.
- Wang, X., & Huang, J. (2006). The relationships between key stakeholders' project performance and project success: Perceptions of Chinese construction supervising engineers. *International journal of project management*, 24, 253.